

IMPACT OF COMMUNITY-BASED PHYSIOTHERAPY ON FUNCTIONAL OUTCOMES IN ORTHOPEDICALLY HANDICAPPED RURAL CHILDREN POST-SURGERY

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18872310>

How to cite this Article: Tanniru Subbarao^{1*}, Dr. Naga Satish Kumar Buraka² (2026). Impact Of Community-Based Physiotherapy On Functional Outcomes In Orthopedically Handicapped Rural Children Post-Surgery. European Journal of Biomedical and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 13(3), 388–393.

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Article Received on 05/02/2026

Article Revised on 25/02/2026

Article Published on 01/03/2026

ABSTRACT

Background and Purpose: Orthopedic disabilities in rural Indian children, often due to congenital conditions, neglected trauma, or cerebral palsy sequelae, frequently result in delayed surgical intervention and limited post-operative rehabilitation access. Community-based physiotherapy offers a promising, low-cost solution to improve functional outcomes in resource-constrained settings. This study aimed to evaluate the impact of a 6-week community-based physiotherapy program on gross motor function, functional independence, pain, and quality of life in rural orthopedically handicapped children post-surgery. **Methods:** A single-group quasi-experimental pre-post design was conducted in rural Andhra Pradesh, with 45 children (aged 5–18 years) completing the protocol. Participants received bi-weekly home visits, weekly group sessions, and caregiver training aligned with WHO CBR guidelines. Outcomes were assessed using GMFM-88, WeeFIM, VAS for pain, and PedsQL at baseline and 6 weeks, analyzed via paired t-tests/Wilcoxon tests and regression models. **Results:** Significant improvements were observed: GMFM-88 increased by 15.69 points (d=1.90), WeeFIM by 21 points (d=1.57), VAS pain decreased by 3.45 points (d=-2.59), and PedsQL rose by 16.11 points (d=1.72) (all p<0.001). Pre-scores strongly predicted post-scores (adjusted R² 0.755–0.903) with minimal confounding. **Conclusion:** A short-term community-based physiotherapy program yields substantial functional and quality-of-life gains in rural post-surgical pediatric orthopedic cases, supporting its integration into rural healthcare systems.

KEYWORDS: community-based rehabilitation, physiotherapy, orthopedic disabilities, rural children, post-surgical outcomes, functional independence, India

INTRODUCTION

Orthopedic disabilities in children represent a significant public health challenge in India, particularly in rural areas where access to timely diagnosis, surgical intervention, and rehabilitation remains limited. The overall prevalence of disability in India is estimated at approximately 0.93% to 2.2% of the population, with locomotor disabilities accounting for about 44.73% of all cases, predominantly affecting rural residents.^[1,2] Among children, congenital and acquired orthopedic conditions such as clubfoot (congenital talipes equinovarus), cerebral palsy-related deformities, and post-traumatic impairments contribute substantially to this burden. Clubfoot, one of the most common congenital musculoskeletal anomalies, has a reported birth prevalence of around 1–2 per 1000 live births globally,

with higher rates observed in rural Indian communities (up to 0.9 per 1000 in some surveys).^[3,4] These conditions often lead to long-term functional limitations, including impaired mobility, pain, and reduced participation in daily activities if not addressed promptly.

Surgical interventions, such as corrective osteotomy, tendon release, or clubfoot surgery, are frequently required to restore alignment and function in these children. However, in rural India, delayed presentation due to poor transportation infrastructure, low socioeconomic status, reliance on traditional remedies, and limited awareness frequently results in neglected or advanced deformities, complicating surgical outcomes.^[5,6] Post-operative rehabilitation is critical for optimizing recovery, preventing complications such as

contractures or muscle atrophy, and achieving functional independence. Yet, rural settings face substantial barriers to effective rehabilitation, including scarcity of specialized physiotherapists, long travel distances to healthcare facilities, financial constraints, and inadequate follow-up services.^[7,8]

Community-based rehabilitation (CBR), endorsed by the World Health Organization, offers a promising, low-cost, and contextually appropriate strategy to bridge these gaps by delivering services directly within communities through trained local workers, family involvement, and home- or group-based interventions.^[9] In rural India, CBR models have demonstrated potential in improving access to physiotherapy, enhancing adherence, and supporting post-surgical recovery for children with disabilities.^[10] Physiotherapy plays a pivotal role in post-operative care by promoting range of motion, muscle strengthening, gait training, pain management, and activities of daily living, ultimately contributing to better motor function, reduced dependency, and improved quality of life.^[11,12]

Despite growing evidence supporting community-based approaches, there remains a paucity of studies specifically examining the impact of structured community-based physiotherapy on functional outcomes in rural Indian children following orthopedic surgery. This gap is particularly evident in regions like Andhra Pradesh, where rural socioeconomic and infrastructural challenges exacerbate disability burdens. The present study aimed to assess the effects of a 6-week community-based physiotherapy program on key functional outcomes—including gross motor function (Gross Motor Function Measure-88), functional independence (WeeFIM), pain levels (Visual Analogue Scale), and health-related quality of life (Pediatric Quality of Life Inventory)—in orthopedically handicapped rural children post-surgery. By addressing these outcomes in a real-world rural context, this research seeks to provide evidence for scalable, cost-effective rehabilitation models that can reduce long-term disability and promote inclusive development for affected children.

METHODOLOGY

The study used a single-group quasi-experimental pre-post design without a concurrent control arm. All participants received the same community-based physiotherapy intervention. Baseline assessments were conducted prior to the program, with outcomes re-evaluated after 6 weeks. Within-group changes were the primary focus, with historical hospital-based follow-up data from similar rural pediatric populations used for context.

Conducted in rural Andhra Pradesh—an agrarian region with limited specialized orthopedic and rehabilitation services and high prevalence of pediatric orthopedic disabilities from congenital conditions, neglected trauma, and cerebral palsy sequelae—participants were recruited via primary health centers, ASHAs, and orthopedic outreach camps.

Eligible children (aged 5–18 years) had a diagnosed orthopedic handicap (e.g., clubfoot, cerebral palsy-related deformities, congenital limb discrepancies, post-traumatic impairments), corrective surgery within the prior 3–6 months, baseline functional limitation (e.g., GMFM <80%), and caregiver/child willingness to participate. Exclusions included significant unrelated comorbidities, concurrent intensive hospital rehabilitation, or planned relocation. Convenience sampling drew from primary health center referrals, surgical camps, and community networks. Target sample size was 50; 45 completed the protocol (attrition mainly from loss to follow-up or incomplete attendance).

The 6-week community-based physiotherapy program followed WHO CBR guidelines^[8], emphasizing low-cost, family-centered, community-delivered strategies for rural low-resource settings. Delivered by trained physiotherapists with ASHA support, it targeted post-surgical recovery in conditions such as clubfoot correction, tendon lengthening, and deformity management. Goals included improved gross motor function, functional independence, pain reduction, contracture prevention, caregiver empowerment, and long-term community integration, using a phased intensive structure for acute and sub-acute recovery.^[13,14]

The intervention included bi-weekly 45–60-minute home visits, weekly 1-hour group sessions (5–10 children) at anganwadi centers or community halls, and caregiver education with workshops in Weeks 1 and 4. Direct contact averaged 10–12 hours per participant, plus daily 15–30-minute home exercises using local materials (e.g., rice bags, household furniture). Senior physiotherapist supervision ensured $\geq 80\%$ fidelity via logs and checks. Weekly VAS pain and functional monitoring guided adjustments, with PHC referral for complications. Exercises progressed from passive/assisted to active/independent (10–15 reps/set, 2–3 sets), intensity titrated to Borg 3–5/10, stopping if pain $> 5/10$ VAS. This aligns with evidence of functional gains from short-term community-delivered rehabilitation in pediatric orthopedic and cerebral palsy populations in low- and middle-income countries.^[13,14]

The detailed week-by-week intervention schedule is presented in the table below:

Week	Phase Focus	Home Visits (Bi-weekly, 45–60 min)	Group Sessions (Weekly, 1 hour)	Caregiver Training Focus	Key Goals / Progression Criteria
1	Acute mobilization	Passive/assisted range of motion; scar massage; elevation; gentle heel slides/ankle pumps	Seated circle activities; deep breathing for pain relief	Wound care; signs of complications; basic daily routine (10 min home exercises)	Reduce pain 20–30%; initiate early mobilization
2	Building basic mobility	Active-assisted range of motion; weight-shifting in sitting/standing; towel-assisted stretches	Light games (e.g., balloon toss for coordination)	Assisting transfers (bed to chair); pain log monitoring	Improve joint flexibility; achieve assisted standing 1–2 min
3	Strength development	Isometric strengthening (e.g., quadriceps/glute sets); resisted hip abduction/adduction with rice bags	Partner exercises for balance; seated marches	Home adaptations (e.g., furniture support)	Increase muscle strength; reduce basic ADL dependency
4	Balance and gait training	Dynamic balance (e.g., one-leg stand with support); marching/gait drills	Relay games for gait; ADL simulations	Fall prevention; long-term home program workshop	Enhance stability; achieve independent short-distance walking
5	Functional integration	Task-specific training (e.g., stair simulation); play-based coordination (e.g., kicking ball)	Community outing simulation; peer feedback	Independence strategies; sustainability post-program	Improve ADLs; boost psychosocial aspects via groups
6	Consolidation & discharge	Review/advanced strengthening (e.g., supported squats); final progress review	Celebration session with family; success sharing	Personalized home program booklet; ASHA follow-up links	Solidify gains; prepare for self-management (80% home adherence)

Primary functional outcomes were assessed at baseline and 6 weeks post-intervention using the Gross Motor Function Measure (GMFM-88),^[10,15] the WeeFIM (Functional Independence Measure for Children),^[12,16] and the Visual Analogue Scale for pain. The secondary outcome was health-related quality of life, measured with the Pediatric Quality of Life Inventory (PedsQL™ 4.0 Generic Core Scales).^[17,18,19] All instruments were translated into Telugu where necessary and pilot-tested for cultural appropriateness with 10 non-study participants.

Data analysis with descriptive statistics summarized participant characteristics and outcome scores. Pre-post comparisons were conducted with paired t-tests for normally distributed data or Wilcoxon signed-rank tests for non-parametric data. Effect sizes were reported using Cohen's d. Multiple regression models adjusted for

potential confounders, including age, gender, and type of surgery. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS

The statistical analysis of the data from the single-group quasi-experimental pre-post study (N = 45 completed participants) evaluating the impact of a 6-week community-based physiotherapy program on functional outcomes in rural orthopedically handicapped children post-surgery. Analyses including descriptive statistics, normality assessments (Shapiro-Wilk test), pre-post comparisons (paired t-tests for normally distributed data or Wilcoxon signed-rank tests for non-normal data), effect size calculations (Cohen's d), and multiple linear regression models adjusting for potential confounders (age, gender, socioeconomic status, surgery type, and disability cause). P-values < 0.05 were considered statistically significant.

Participant Characteristics

Table 2: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of Participants (N = 45)

Characteristic	Category	n (%) or Mean ± SD
Age (years)		12.40 ± 3.97
Gender	Male	12 (48.9%)
	Female	11 (51.1%)
Socioeconomic Status	Low	24 (53.3%)
	Middle	18 (40.0%)
	High	3 (6.7%)

Surgery Type	Clubfoot Surgery	18 (40.0%)
	Osteotomy	13 (28.9%)
	Tendon Release	14 (31.1%)
Disability Cause	Congenital	23 (51.1%)
	CP-related	12 (26.7%)
	Trauma-related	10 (22.2%)

The sample was representative of rural pediatric orthopedic populations in Andhra Pradesh, with a near-equal gender distribution and a mean age of approximately 11.4 years. The majority of participants belonged to low or middle socioeconomic strata (93.3%), reflecting the socioeconomic profile of rural communities. Clubfoot surgery was the most frequent

procedure (40.0%), followed by tendon release and osteotomy, while congenital etiologies predominated (51.1%). These characteristics align with the thesis focus on rural orthopedically handicapped children and support the generalizability of findings to similar underserved settings.

Descriptive Statistics of Outcome Measures

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics for Outcome Measures Before and After Intervention (N = 45).

Outcome Measure	Pre-Intervention Mean (SD)	Post-Intervention Mean (SD)	Mean Difference (Post – Pre)
GMFM-88 (%)	56.63 (8.23)	72.32 (8.50)	+15.69
WeeFIM (total score)	78.80 (13.30)	99.76 (13.75)	+20.96
VAS for Pain (0–10)	5.85 (1.16)	2.40 (1.51)	–3.45
PedsQL Total Score (0–100)	66.15 (8.90)	82.26 (9.98)	+16.11

Baseline scores indicated moderate to severe functional impairment and pain levels typical of post-surgical rural children with orthopedic disabilities. Post-intervention means showed clinically meaningful improvements across all domains: gross motor function increased by approximately 16 percentage points, functional

independence by nearly 21 points, pain reduced by more than half, and health-related quality of life improved by 16 points. These changes suggest that the community-based physiotherapy program produced substantial gains in motor performance, daily living skills, pain control, and overall well-being.

Pre-Post Comparison Results

Table 4: Pre-Post Statistical Comparisons and Effect Sizes (N = 45)

Outcome Measure	Test Used	Test Statistic	p-value	Mean/Median Difference	Cohen's d	Effect Size Interpretation
GMFM-88	Paired t-test	t = 35.05	<0.001	+15.69	1.90	Large
WeeFIM	Wilcoxon signed-rank test	Z = –5.84	<0.001	+21 (median)	1.57	Large
VAS for Pain	Wilcoxon signed-rank test	Z = –5.84	<0.001	–3.45 (median)	–2.59	Large
PedsQL Total	Wilcoxon signed-rank test	Z = –5.84	<0.001	+16.11 (median)	1.72	Large

All outcome measures demonstrated highly statistically significant improvements ($p < 0.001$) following the 6-week intervention. The large effect sizes (Cohen's d ranging from 1.57 to 2.59 in absolute value) indicate not only statistical significance but also strong clinical relevance. The greatest standardized improvement was

observed in pain reduction ($d = -2.59$), followed by gross motor function ($d = 1.90$) and quality of life ($d = 1.72$). These robust effects support the efficacy of the community-based physiotherapy program in enhancing functional recovery and reducing disability burden in rural pediatric orthopedic cases.

Multiple Linear Regression Analyses

Table 5: Summary of Multiple Linear Regression Models for Post-Intervention Outcomes (N = 45)

Dependent Variable	Primary Predictor (Pre-score)	β (standardized)	p-value (pre-score)	Adjusted R ²	Model F-statistic	Model p-value	Significant Confounders (p < 0.05)
Post-GMFM-88	Pre-GMFM-88	0.93	<0.001	0.896	38.58	<0.001	None
Post-WeeFIM	Pre-WeeFIM	0.96	<0.001	0.903	41.97	<0.001	Socioeconomic status (marginal, p=0.054)
Post-VAS Pain	Pre-VAS	1.15	<0.001	0.755	13.85	<0.001	None
Post-PedsQL Total	Pre-PedsQL	1.02	<0.001	0.847	24.82	<0.001	None

The Multiple linear regression models explained a high proportion of variance in post-intervention outcomes (adjusted R² = 0.755–0.903), with pre-intervention scores being the strongest and most consistent predictors (all $\beta > 0.93$, $p < 0.001$). After controlling for age, gender, socioeconomic status, surgery type, and disability cause, the intervention effect remained highly significant and largely independent of demographic and clinical confounders. The marginal negative association between socioeconomic status and post-WeeFIM scores ($p = 0.054$) suggests that children from lower socioeconomic backgrounds may experience slightly smaller gains in functional independence, though this did not reach statistical significance. Overall, the regression results reinforce that baseline function is the primary determinant of post-intervention outcomes, and the community-based physiotherapy program produced consistent, meaningful improvements across the sample.

DISCUSSION

The present study shows that a 6-week community-based physiotherapy program in rural Andhra Pradesh, produced highly significant and clinically meaningful improvements in orthopedically handicapped children post-surgery. Gains included a mean +15.69 points on GMFM-88 ($d = 1.90$), median +21 points on WeeFIM ($d = 1.57$), mean –3.45 points on VAS pain ($d = -2.59$), and mean +16.11 points on PedsQL ($d = 1.72$). These large effect sizes support the value of community-delivered rehabilitation in rural settings with limited specialized services.

These results align with evidence from low- and middle-income countries on community-based rehabilitation (CBR) for children with physical disabilities. Balaji *et al.* (2024) reported similar gains in gross motor function and independence in rural South India through multidisciplinary community interventions.^[9] Short-term intensive physiotherapy, including group and task-oriented training, has shown medium to large effects on motor performance and daily activities in cerebral palsy and post-surgical orthopedic cases, as demonstrated by Ko *et al.* (2020) and Kuroda *et al.* (2022).^[15,16] The strong pain reduction effect ($d = -2.59$) is consistent with reports of effective community-delivered physiotherapy

for post-operative pain and complication prevention in pediatric populations in resource-limited settings.^[13,14]

Multiple regression analyses indicated pre-intervention scores as the strongest predictors of post-intervention outcomes ($\beta > 0.93$, adjusted R² 0.755–0.903), with minimal confounding from age, gender, surgery type, or disability cause. A marginal negative link between lower socioeconomic status and post-WeeFIM scores ($p = 0.054$) suggests slightly smaller gains in poorer households, though not statistically significant and not diminishing overall efficacy. These findings confirm the program's consistent benefits across baseline characteristics, reinforcing its applicability in rural Indian contexts.

Strengths include real-world rural implementation addressing travel, cost, and specialist shortages via home visits, group sessions at anganwadi centers, and caregiver training, aligned with WHO CBR guidelines.^[8] Validated, culturally adapted measures (GMFM-88, WeeFIM, VAS, PedsQL) with Telugu translations ensured reliable assessment.^[10,12,17-20] Large effect sizes and strong model fit provide robust quantitative support.

Limitations include the single-group pre-post design lacking a concurrent control, increasing risk of maturation or history effects. Historical benchmarking offered context but could not fully control external factors. Convenience sampling (45 completers from 50) may introduce bias, the short 6-week duration limits long-term insight, and 10% attrition (mainly from migration) may affect representativeness. Proxy PedsQL reports and partial blinding pose minor bias risks, though independent assessors were used for primary measures.

Future research should include randomized controlled trials, longer follow-up (6–12 months) to assess sustainability, multi-center studies for generalizability, and qualitative data on caregiver experiences and implementation. In summary, this study provides strong preliminary evidence that low-cost, community-based physiotherapy can meaningfully improve post-surgical functional outcomes in rural orthopedically handicapped children, supporting its integration into primary

healthcare systems to reduce disability burden in underserved areas of India.

CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates that a 6-week community-based physiotherapy program significantly improves gross motor function (GMFM-88 +15.69 points, $d=1.90$), functional independence (WeeFIM +21 points, $d=1.57$), pain levels (VAS -3.45 points, $d=-2.59$), and quality of life (PedsQL +16.11 points, $d=1.72$) in rural orthopedically handicapped children post-surgery. Delivered through home visits, group sessions, and caregiver training using local resources, the intervention proved effective, feasible, and largely independent of demographic confounders in a resource-limited setting.

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